

DCMS AI Pilot Project Report

Automatic Text Extraction of MDA Data Cards using Large Language Models

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1 Project

1.1 Aim

This project aims to leverage large language models (LLMs) to perform automatic text extraction on standardised data cards used for specimen documentation in the Lyme Regis Museum (LRM). Through tailoring an OpenAI large language model to recognise, extract and accurately categorise handwritten text on data cards, we provide a solution that can quickly and accurately convert physical records into digital text in structured file format (e.g., JSON and CSV). As digitisation has become quintessential across institutions, we aim to provide this solution to assist in making collections globally accessible to both researchers and the public, improve museum communications and contribute to long-term digital preservation and specimen legacy at the LRM. Furthermore, as these standardised Museum Documentation Association (MDA) data cards are widely used across non-national museums in the UK, this model has the potential to scale beyond the LRM, facilitating the digitisation of Natural Science and Geology collections nationwide.

1.2 Background

Geology and natural history museums worldwide house invaluable collections that serve as a vital record of life on Earth. However, of the two billion natural history specimens held globally, approximately 99% remain in storage rather than on public display (Marshall et al., 2018; Rogers, 2016). Furthermore, the majority of specimens remain undocumented or undigitized, with such uncaptured data termed “dark data” (Marshall et al., 2018). Dark data does not only incur financial and carbon costs on researchers who must

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physically travel to museums to access specimens and corresponding metadata, but further limits museum outreach, public accessibility and negates long-term digital preservation of collections (Tan et al., 2022). This issue is particularly evident in global fossil records, whereby the Palaeobiology Database, the leading open-access palaeontological database, currently accounts for only 3 - 4% of all known fossil localities (Marshall et al., 2018).

Recent technological advancements have generated a significant rise in museum data digitisation. Digitisation in museums involves the usage of a centralised online or cloud-based database, populated with catalogued specimens and their corresponding metadata such as georeferenced locality data, date of obtainment, images of the specimens and legacy data (Miller et al., 2020). When properly structured and integrated with functions such as searchable text catalogues, these digital databases enhance collection management, facilitate research accessibility and public engagement. However, manual digitisation is both resource-intensive and time consuming. In particular, smaller museums who suffer from underfunding or understaffing may struggle processing vast amounts of data stored in their institutions (Marshall et al., 2018).

The Lyme Regis Museum (LRM), located along the Jurassic Coast World Heritage site in Dorset, holds one of the most important collections of early Jurassic paleontological specimens in the UK, boasting both historic and contemporary collections that have built a strong scientific legacy. The LRM utilises standardised Museums Documentation Association (MDA) data cards to record essential specimen information (Trust, 2025). However, as these records are handwritten and transcription is not yet supported by an automated tool, curators must manually transcribe data into the museum's collection management system (CMS), Axiell. This time-consuming process diverts staff efforts from collection maintenance and data validation.

Recently, a surge in machine learning advancements have shown significant potential to accelerate data digitisation. In particular, large language models such as OpenAI's ChatGPT and Anthropic's Claude have been effective in text data extraction from images and PDF files (Anthropic, 2023; Brown et al., 2020). LLMs have consistently achieved high accuracy in extracting printed text, where Lehnen et al. (2024) demonstrated OpenAI's GPT-4 successfully extracted 94% of the 2,800 neuroradiology reports accurately, requiring no further post processing. Similarly, scientific publications have been extracted with Claude 2 at an accuracy of 95% (Gartlehner et al., 2024). There is also promise in extracting more complex and unpredictable handwritten text, as demonstrated by Salili-James et al. (2024), who successfully utilised OpenAI's LLMs to transcribe handwritten bird egg index cards.

This project aims to utilise LLMs to recognise, extract and accurately categorise the handwritten data within MDA data cards, allowing an efficient conversion of physical records into digital text to populate the LRM's online CMS (Axiell). More broadly, as MDA data cards are used across several non-national museums in the UK, this solution may open doors for digitization in smaller institutions with limited staff, modernising their

record keeping and preserving specimen records nationwide.

2 Dataset and Methods

2.1 Raw Dataset and Data Preprocessing

The LRM provided 722 scanned PDF files of the MDA data cards. The cards were structured in a table format, containing categorical fields written within each row and corresponding data beneath the field headings (Figure 1). To process the cards into a format appropriate to feed into the LLM model, we conducted preprocessing through a Python script. This included converting the PDF files into JPG images and resizing the images to 1000 by 1500 pixels. Further, as each card was double sided, the two PDF pages were combined into a single image for each card. Resizing and combing both sides of the cards reduced the computational power needed to run all the cards through the model.

Field	Value
IDENTIFICATION	File: GEOLOGY Institution - identity number: LYMPH: 1973.6 Part: Simple name: BRACHIOPOD Form: FOSSIL Number: Classified identification or full name: CALCIRHYNCHIA CALCARIA (BUCKMAN)
COLLECTION	Name(s): SEVEN ROCK POINT, WEST OF LYME REGIS Locality number: Loc Long: Other co-ordinates: value & units/accuracy: Altitude: Other position: value & units/accuracy: Depth: Complex: Zone: JURASSIC; LOWER JURASSIC; HETTANGIAN OR SINEMURIAN Rock: Age: LIAS GROUP; LOWER LIAS SUBGROUP; BLUE LIAS FORMATION Complex: Zone: Rock: Age: Complex: Zone: Stratigraphy detail: Locality detail:
STORAGE	Collection method: LYN KANSON Collector - date: W.D. LANG; DATE UNKNOWN Collector number: Store - date: 6-1-2005 Recorder - date: PADDY HOWE; 6-1-2005
ACQUISITION	Acquisition number: Assumed from - date: W.D. LANG; DATE UNKNOWN D. Price: Conditions: D. Yes/No: Valuation - date:
DESCRIPTION	Condition known/detail: FAIR Condition known/detail: NEAR COMPLETE Dimension measured: value & units/accuracy: MAXIMUM WIDTH: 11mm ± low Dimension measured: value & units/accuracy: Part - name - description key/detail: NEAR COMPLETE SPECIMEN WITH SOME WEAR ON DORSAL VALVE
NOTES	Construction: Other process: Method/detail - operator - date - detail: Cross reference: Reproduction: Construction: Reproduction: 1. Date: Author - date - title - journal or publisher - volume - detail: Cross reference: 1. Date: Author - date - title - journal or publisher - volume - detail: Drawing or photo:
OTES	Note in the catalogue of the Geological Collection this specimen is listed as having come from the "top of copper shales". This is probably a mistake, as there is no horizon called the copper shales. It is probable that this specimen is from the top copper shales (top of Lias) and that the collector would have made such an error, and probably the person compiling the catalogue has taken "top copper shales" to mean "the top of the copper shales".

Figure 1: Example of a MDA data card populated with data from the Lyme Regis Museum.

2.2 Methods Overview

The project involved 5 main stages (Figure 2). First, prompt engineering was conducted to develop an effective prompt for extracting and categorizing data, ensuring data was assigned to the correct categorical field. Once finalised, a Python script was used to encode and process 722 card images by sending them to the OpenAI model via its application programming interface (API). Parameters such as temperature and max tokens were adjusted to fine-tune responses according to project requirements. The model generated 722 structured JSON outputs, with each JSON file corresponding to a card and contained extracted data fields and associated data. Next, post-processing was applied to refine the extracted data, particularly correcting issues in complex fields, such as vertically stacked text. The final JSON files were then evaluated by statistical comparison against ground truth data, to validate accuracy and reproducibility. Finally, all JSON files were consolidated into a single CSV file, ready for integration into the LRM’s online database.

Figure 2: A flow chart visualising the 5 main stages of the project methodology: prompt engineering, processing cards through the LLM, post processing, model evaluation and production of the final CSV deliverable.

2.3 LLM Model Approach

The LLM model architecture utilised for this project is GPT-4o. Developed by OpenAI, it is an iteration of the Generative Pre-trained Transformer (GPT) model (Brown et al., 2020). Trained on over 300 billion words, this revolutionary model incorporates transformer-based models to process data in parallel, unlike traditional language models programmed to use statistics to predict subsequent words (Alberts et al., 2023).

Prompt engineering is essential to tune and guide the LLM to perform a distinct task. Through iterative trials, we developed a prompt that accurately recognised card structure, field categories and extracted handwritten text within each field. Since the data format in the online database/CMS differs from the card structure, the prompt was refined to account for instances where new fields were created or existing fields were split.

Additionally, the prompt was adjusted to handle special cases, such as crossed-out text, text outside table boundaries and symbols such as “[]” and “?”, which are crucial symbols in geology curation to indicate uncertainty of specimen classification.

Once the prompt was finalised, 722 card images were processed through the GPT-4o API. This process involved iterating through a directory of images, encoding them into a base64 format and sending them to the OpenAI GPT-4o API to process. The API request was constructed with the finalised text prompt, the encoded image, adjusted parameter values (temperature = 0.1, max tokens = 2048, frequency penalty = 0 and presence penalty = 0), along with a response format set to JSON object. These tailored parameters ensured that the model prioritised accuracy, consistency and controlled output length, keeping the extracted data reliable and structured across the 722 cards. For example, the low temperature parameter ensured highly deterministic outputs, while setting presence penalty to 0 prevented the introduction of new concepts beyond the text prompt. In total, the model generated 722 JSON files, with each card processed in approximately 18 seconds.

2.4 Post-Processing

While the model accurately captured the majority of the data present on the cards, challenges arose with extracting vertically stacked text (Figure 3). This issue stemmed from limitations in GPT-4o’s vision processing capabilities, which are trained to recognize objects, patterns, and text in standard layouts (left to right, top to bottom). Vertical text formatting disrupts this standard, leading to incorrect recognition and misalignment.

Complex	Zone	Stratigraphy keyword/detail
Rock	Age	Jurassic : Pliensbachian
Complex	Zone	Lias : Lower Lias : Charmouth Mudstone : Green Ammonite : [Bed 126] [Red Bed]
Rock	Age	Group : Subgroup : Fm
Complex	Zone	[Dawoei Zone] : [Capricornus Subzone] : [PbH21 - Crescens Bishoran]
Rock	Age	

Figure 3: An example of vertically stacked words within the “Chronostratigraphy” field highlighted by the red box.

Two fields, “Lithostratigraphy” and “Biostratigraphy”, present vertically stacked data. However, both follow a consistent, predictable structure due to their descriptions of rock strata. With this fixed format, once the model correctly extracts a portion of the final keyword, the beginning and middle sections can be reconstructed correctly. For instance, when the model extracts “Bed 74d” from the “Lithostratigraphy” field, the post-processing pipeline replaces it with the full description: “Lias group; Lower Lias Subgroup; Charmouth Mudstone Fm; Shales with Beef Mbr; Bed 74d Brooki Bed”. Since geological strata information follows a consistent structure across institutions, this approach can be

generalized to other geological collections.

2.5 Validation and Final Deliverable

The final JSON files were statistically evaluated against a set of ground truth data. Ground truth data consists of a random selection of 50 cards with their data manually extracted to ensure accuracy and reliability. Several metrics were employed to evaluate the effectiveness of the data extraction pipeline, both before and after the post-processing phase. This approach facilitated a comparison between the raw model output and the refinements made through post-processing.

To assess reproducibility, Levenshtein Distance and Fuzzy Ratio metrics were examined (SeatGeek, 2020; Yujian and Bo, 2007). Additional evaluation metrics, Word Accuracy and Token Sort Ratio, were also investigated (Jitsi, 2025). Levenshtein distance calculates the minimum number of edits (insertions, deletions, or substitutions) required to change one string into another. Fuzzy Ratio evaluates text similarity by applying fuzzy string matching techniques, allowing for minor variations in punctuation and spelling. Token Sort Ratio compares two strings by splitting them into individual tokens and removes the impact of word order. Word accuracy measures the exact number of differences between strings and is the strictest of the metrics, penalising word order, minor misspellings and wrong words with equal impact.

This range of metrics enabled investigation of both strict and more lenient differences between the model’s outputs and the ground truth data. Once evaluation metrics satisfied project requirements, all JSON files were consolidated into a single CSV file, ready for integration into the LRM’s online database.

3 Model Results and Final Performance

Model evaluation metrics displayed strong performance across categorical fields, as illustrated in Table 1. A large number of results cluster around the 90 to 100% range, with 12 fields such as “Class”, “File”, “Form” and “Institution” scoring 100% consistently. Across all fields, the overall averages for mean Levenshtein Distance, Fuzzy Ratio, Token Sort Ratio and Word Accuracy are 91.23%, 91.89%, 92.08% and 84.58% respectively.

Post processing further showed improvements in the fields “Lithostratigraphy” and “Biostratigraphy” that contained complex, vertically stacked words, with improvements ranging from 3.00 to 14.86% across all evaluation metrics (Table 2).

Table 1: Mean Levenshtein Distance, Fuzzy Ratio, Token Sort Ratio, and Word Accuracy across all fields of 50 ground truth data cards. Values closer to 100% are colored green, closer to 50% in yellow, and 0% in red.

Field Category	Mean Levenshtein	Mean Fuzzy Ratio	Mean Token Sort Ratio	Mean Word Accuracy
Acquired date	86.60	88.02	88.00	76.00
Acquired from	67.91	69.98	71.18	53.90
Acquisition method	81.80	84.24	86.58	82.00
Author: date: title: journal or publisher: volume: det	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00
Class	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00
Classified identification or full name	94.63	96.24	96.48	75.32
Collection method	62.32	63.08	62.79	58.33
Collector: date	65.74	65.92	65.88	63.54
Completeness keyword/detail	84.31	84.46	86.46	84.00
Condition keyword/detail	98.00	98.00	98.00	98.00
Conservation	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00
Cross-reference	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00
File	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00
Form	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00
Identifier: date	91.51	91.70	91.70	87.60
Institution	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00
Locality detail	99.86	99.94	99.08	98.98
Method/detail: operator: date: detail	91.46	91.64	91.52	89.66
NGR	93.75	94.41	94.14	92.09
Notes	95.11	95.46	95.64	92.25
Object Entry	99.60	99.78	99.34	96.00
Object Number	93.15	93.40	97.52	60.00
Other process	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00
Place names/detail	97.75	98.37	98.08	91.43
Price	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00
Recorder: date	92.81	94.62	95.86	64.00
Reproduction	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00
Simple name	97.25	98.30	98.46	89.00
Status	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00
Store: date	79.78	84.20	83.38	49.25
Stratigraphy detail	93.73	93.73	93.47	92.94
Biostratigraphy	84.56	85.64	84.96	75.71
Chronostratigraphy	96.75	97.36	99.84	68.00
Lithostratigraphy	90.79	93.44	94.52	76.94
System	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00
value & units/accuracy	45.16	46.00	42.06	30.00

Table 2: Post-processing improvement for vertically stacked text, evaluating mean Levenshtein Distance, Fuzzy Ratio, Token Sort Ratio and Word Accuracy for field categories "Biostratigraphy" and "Lithostratigraphy".

Mean Evaluation Metric	Field Category	Raw Model Output (%)	Post Process Output (%)	Improvement (%)
Levenshtein Distance	Biostratigraphy	80.04	84.56	+4.52
	Lithostratigraphy	77.92	90.79	+12.87
Fuzzy Ratio	Biostratigraphy	82.48	85.64	+3.16
	Lithostratigraphy	84.80	93.44	+8.64
Token Sort Ratio	Biostratigraphy	81.96	84.96	+3.00
	Lithostratigraphy	87.56	94.52	+6.96
Word Accuracy	Biostratigraphy	60.85	75.71	+14.86
	Lithostratigraphy	67.47	76.94	+9.47

4 Discussion and Project Implications

4.1 Discussion of Model Performance

The strong performance of our LLM model demonstrates that it successfully extracts handwritten data and assigns it to the correct fields with accuracy, speed and efficiency. Importantly, the model pipeline enables the processing of all 722 data cards in just 6 hours, a significant reduction compared to the approximate 300 hours (or 37.5 workdays) required for manual processing. This translates to time savings of approximately 98%. Utilisation of this model ensures a more efficient digitisation workflow at the LRM, lessening data entry pressures on curators and allowing them to focus on crucial data validation and collection enhancement work. Ultimately, the digitised card images and extracted data will be stored and publicly presented on LRM's CMS (Axiell) in 18 months time. The data will further be offered to DiSSCo and other portals such as the Collections Trust.

The model evaluation demonstrates strong model performance. Across all fields, the overall averages for the four metrics range from 84.58% to 92.08%. This demonstrates that the model's output is largely aligned with the ground truth, with only minor adjustments or reordering required for both strings to match identically. Furthermore, post-processing significantly refined the results, leading to an increase of up to 14.86% in evaluation metric scores. Most importantly, with processing each card taking 18 seconds, the model has produced time savings of approximately 98%, utilising 6 hours over 300 hours to process all 722 data cards.

However, certain fields show lower performance metrics, particularly "value & units/accuracy" and "collector: date." This is likely due to the presence of numbers in varying formats and special symbols that the model struggles to extract correctly. For instance, dates are often recorded in different formats depending on the curator, such as 10.11.2012 and 10/11/2012. Additionally, "value & units/accuracy" frequently contains the symbol "±", which the LLM has difficulty interpreting and extracting.

Despite these limitations, discussions with the project owners at the LRM highlighted that achieving 100% across all evaluation metrics is not the primary objective. The key priority is ensuring that the vast majority of information is extracted to an acceptable standard. This is due to the fact that, following data extraction, a validation process is still required, regardless of whether the data was extracted manually or by AI. Errors or inaccuracies are inherent in the cards themselves, and only curators validating the cards can ultimately correct the data before it is uploaded to the online database. As a result, the current performance metrics of the model are considered more than adequate for this specific use case. Upon receiving the final deliverable, the project owners confirmed that the data extracted by this pipeline will be publicly and openly accessible on Axiell by August 2025, demonstrating how quick the digitisation process can be.

4.2 Other Project Impacts

Beyond the immediate positive impact of the AI pipeline for data extraction, this pilot project has also significantly benefitted the LRM in terms of digitisation. The acquisition of a flatbed scanner has positioned the LRM as a digitisation hub for the Southwest region. Museums with limited curatorial staff or those reliant on volunteers now have access to a cost-effective and time-efficient method of digitising their documents through shared use of the scanner.

For example, discussions have taken place with the Dorset Museum & Art Gallery regarding the digitisation of physical journal entries for inclusion in an online, open-access database in PDF format. The newly acquired flatbed scanner would play a pivotal role in facilitating this process. Furthermore, this project has strengthened the LRM's application for the Designation Scheme Award, which recognizes and celebrates outstanding collections of international and national importance in England. If achieved, this award will raise the LRM collection's profile and highlight its cultural value across the UK, ensuring the museums legacy into the future.

4.3 Future Directions

Future applications of the model will require two key phases for successful implementation: 1) enhancing the model pipeline, and 2) making the model accessible to institutions by improving its scalability and versatility.

Further adjustments and trials with the model pipeline, given additional time, could improve the overall results. More rigorous pre-processing trials could help ensure that the cards are optimally formatted for the model. Deionising the images could reduce noise, minimising random pixel value variations. Additionally, implementing text region detection may assist the model in identifying and processing multiple text regions on the cards. Trials with image segmentation or deep-learning techniques such as CTPNs (Connectionist Text Proposal Networks) could also aid in extracting the complex table format present on the cards (Tian et al., 2016). Moreover, experimenting with alternative LLM models, such as Claude2 or Deepseek, would allow for comparative testing and analysis of the most effective model to use (Anthropic, 2023; DeepSeek-AI et al., 2025).

The final stage of expanding this project to its full potential will involve preparing it for use across UK museum institutions in a flexible and scalable manner. In total, this can positively impact up to 1700 museums that are currently within the MDA association (Collections Trust, 2020). Expansion to this stage may include testing the generalisation of the model across different card collections, as the cards are used not only for Geology collections but also for Zoology and Palaeontology collections. Linking the pipeline to automatically connect with online databases could further enhance its effectiveness and adoption across museums, appealing to saving curators valuable time and digitising their collections for future use.

5 Conclusion

In conclusion, our model pipeline for automatic text extraction can significantly enhance the efficiency and accuracy of digitising MDA data cards. By leveraging LLMs to extract and categorise data from these cards, this solution not only saves curator's time by 98%, but further contributes in making collections globally accessible to researchers and the public, improve museum communications and assists in long-term digital preservation and specimen legacy. Additionally, this model can scale beyond the LRM and will be especially beneficial for smaller institutions with limited resources that utilise these MDA data cards in their existing collections. Ultimately, this pipeline could act as a tool used across institutions to process and digitise essential information, preserving their vital collections through easy population of their collection databases, ensuring that information is accessible and available for generations to come.

Supplementary Materials

The code for this project is available to view on [GitHub](#).

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